

***Variarum scripturarum exempla*, Willem Silvius' writing-book discovered¹**

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Abstract: This article attributes a manuscript in the collection of the KB, the National Library of the Netherlands, to Willem Silvius (c. 1520-1580), an Antwerp printer and a former writing master. The manuscript carries the title *Variarum scripturarum exempla* and contains 44 writing samples in eight different languages. It probably served as Silvius' personal writing-book, which he used to attract customers when he was working as a writing master in Louvain. In 1562 he intended to publish the manuscript as the first printed exemplar-book in the Low Countries which contained writing models for different languages and settings. Although this publication never materialised, Silvius' writing-book is a testimonial for the life and the achievements of one of most significant printers of sixteenth century Antwerp.

Keywords: Writing-book, Willem Silvius, Manuscript, Calligraphy, Antwerp, Sixteenth Century

On the 5th of January 1562, the Antwerp printer Willem Silvius (c. 1520-1580) was granted a privilege to publish a 'certain book of diverse handwritings such as german, cursive, italian, greek, hebrew and many others, written by him, to learn to write with several decorative capitals and flourishes and with some stories and learned sentences in different languages'.² Researchers have presumed that this privilege was given to Silvius for one of the typographical writing-books that he published after 1562; most likely Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert's *Eenen nieuwen ABC of materi-boeck, inhoudende diversche schoone sententien ende leeringhen*, which was printed in 1564.³ However, that specific booklet was more oriented to service schoolmasters in teaching the writing of letters in their classes or for private tuition. As such, it did not include Greek or Hebrew script as was listed in the privilege. In 2017 I was able to attribute an unidentified manuscript in the collection of the Dutch National Library to Willem Silvius. This manuscript, which carries the title *Variarum scripturarum exempla*, contains writing samples in German, French, Italian, Spanish, Dutch, Latin, Greek and Hebrew.⁴ It

¹ This article is an extended revision of my article for the liber amicorum of Ad Leerintveld, former curator of the KB, National Library of the Netherlands. See: J. Vandommele, 'Aan de jongere die zich toelegt op deze hoogstaande kunstvaardigheid. Het schrijfboek van drukker Willem Silvius', in: *Een oud boeck is oud goud. Studies over bijzondere werken bij het afscheid van Ad Leerintveld als conservator moderne handschriften van de Koninklijke Bibliotheek*, ed. Jan Bos, (e.a.) (Amsterdam 2017), pp. 273-286.

² ARAB Geheime Raad, Oostenrijkse Tijd, 671, f. 121v: 'zekeren boeck van diversche scriften als overlants, cursyff, italiaens, griex, hebreeuw ende meer andere by hem gescreven, leeren scryven met diversche chiraten van menigerley capitalen boecletteren ende stricken ende sommige historien ende leerlycke sentencien in verscheyden spraecken.' The English translation is mostly from M. Mertens, 'Willem Silvius: "Typographical Parent" of John Dee's *Monas Hieroglyphica*', in: *Ambix*, 64:2 (2017), p. 181.

³ H. de la Fontaine Verwey, 'Typografische schrijfboeken. Een hoofdstuk uit de geschiedenis van de civilité-letter', in: H. de la Fontaine Verwey, *Uit de wereld van het boek I. Humanisten en rebellen in de zestiende eeuw*, 2nd edn. (Amsterdam 1976), pp. 133-60, esp. 145-52; Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert, *Eenen nieuwen ABC* (Antwerp, Silvius, 1564). Presently in University Library Amsterdam (OTM: KL 08-29); Mertens, op. cit. (n. 2), p. 181.

⁴ Willem Silvius, *Kalligrafische bundel van Willem Silvius, 1550-1562*. KB, National Library of the Netherlands, The Hague, KW 129 F 2. A digital version of the writing-book of Willem Silvius can be perused at one's own leisure on the website of the KB: www.kb.nl/silvius.

probably served as Silvius' personal writing-book, which he used to attract customers when he was a writing master in Louvain. In 1562 he intended to publish the manuscript as an exemplar-book (a book with examples of different styles of handwriting), hence the requested privilege.⁵ In the following, I will introduce this writing-book and its content, while describing the context in which it was made.

Willem Silvius, *Typographus Regii*

Before discussing the Silvius manuscript, let us first turn to its creator. Willem Silvius was born in 's-Hertogenbosch around 1520 as Willem Verwilt. As a printer, he is often mentioned in unison with Christopher Plantin (c. 1520-1589), his on and off rival and collaborator. Silvius and Plantin were of the same age and started their publishing houses in Antwerp around the same time, Plantin's *Officina Plantiniana* in 1555 and Silvius' *De Gulden Engel* [The Golden Angel] in 1558-1559. Even though Silvius presented himself as a printer in the beginning of his career, research by Paul Valkema Blouw concluded that his printing office did not have its own printing facilities until 1562. All his publications before that year were produced by the presses of other Antwerp printers, such as Christopher Plantin, Ameet Tavenier (c. 1522-1570) and Gilles Coppens van Diest (c. 1496-1572).⁶

Silvius seems to have preferred working that way; using the typesetting-skills of more experienced printers for the actual printing, while he himself took care of the commercial side of affairs: the publishing and selling of the books at his bookshop. It must have been a good business model, since Silvius' career soared early, with him gaining the title of *Typographus Regii* in 1560, after the publication of his first books in 1558-1559, the *Constitutiones Ordinis Velleris aurei* and *Les ordonnances de l'Ordre de la Thoyson d'or*, respectively the Latin and French edition of the statutes of the Order of the Golden Fleece. This prestigious title, which appointed him official printer to the government in Brussels, was offered to Silvius specifically because of the quality of these publications, even though both books were probably printed by Plantin presses at the *Officina Plantiniana*.⁷

By 1561 Silvius decided he needed to have his own printing press. He announced as much when he became a freeman of the Antwerp Saint Luke Guild in the same year, specifically identifying himself as a 'boeckdrucker', a book printer.⁸ The process of transforming his business to include the printing of books was probably accelerated by the absence of Plantin, who resided in Paris in 1562 after a conflict with the authorities caused

⁵ Exemplar books ('exemplaarboeken') or copybooks ('materieboeken') are printed writing books, that contain leaves with examples of different styles of handwriting (in Dutch 'exempelen' or 'materieën'). During most of the sixteenth century, these examples would be reproduced in woodcut. From the 1590's onwards, printers started to publish exemplar-books with engraved reproductions of handwriting. See A.R.A. Croiset van Uchelen, 'Initial books and typographical writing-books from the sixteenth-century Low Countries', in: *Hellinga Festschrift / feestbundel / mélanges*, ed. A.R.A. Croiset van Uchelen, (Amsterdam 1980), p. 111 and T. Croiset van Uchelen, *Jan van den Velde. Schrijfmeester 1569-1623* (Amsterdam 2005), p. 39.

⁶ P. Valkema Blouw, 'Willem Silvius's remarkable start, 1559-1562', in: *Quaerendo* 20 (1990), pp. 420-38.

⁷ Valkema Blouw, op. cit. (n. 6), pp. 420-30.

⁸ *De liggeren en andere historische archieven der Antwerpsche Sint Lucasgilde [...]*, ed. Ph. Rombouts & Th. van Leries (Antwerpen/Den Haag, 1864-1876), Vol. 1, p. 224.

the liquidation of his Antwerp printing office. Silvius bought most of the inventory of the *Officina Plantiniana* during the public auction that followed the bankruptcy. Among which were a couple of typefaces, which he needed to finish a publication of theatre plays he had been working on together with Plantin.⁹ This publication, *Spelen van sinne vol scoone moralisacien wtleggingen ende bediedenissen op alle loeflijcke consten* (1562), contained plays performed by chambers of rhetoric during the so-called Antwerp Landjuweel of 1561.¹⁰ Such an edition of plays was ambitious in scope and the book became the foundation of Silvius' success as a printer and publisher.¹¹ In the next years, he would gain renown for publishing other work by the Dutch rhetoricians (e.g. the plays of the 1561 Rotterdam festival in 1564), Dutch translations of learned books (e.g. Claude Paradin's *Devises héroïques* in 1562) and scholarly work (e.g. John Dee's esoteric work *Monas hieroglyphica* in 1564). Probably his biggest achievement was the publication of Lodovico Guicciardini's *Descrittione di tutti i Paesi Bassi* (1567), an illustrated description of the whole of the Low Countries, which was translated in several different languages and republished many times in the next fifty years.¹²

In 1568, Willem Silvius' life took a bad turn, as he was arrested for his role in the ransacking of the St. Bernard's abbey near Antwerp during the Iconoclastic Fury of 1566. Silvius, who was a close friend of the abbot of the St. Bernard's abbey, Thomas van Tielt (c. 1534-1590), was accused of conspiring with iconoclasts, given that Van Tielt had fled to Germany in the aftermath of the Iconoclastic Fury and had become a protestant minister.¹³ Although Silvius was released after two months, he had to pay a heavy fine. He also lost the favour of the Antwerp government in printing official publications. His printing shop never really recovered from this ordeal. Although Silvius did publish a successful series of French Amadis de Gaule books in the early 1570s, he suffered another setback when Spanish soldiers pillaged Antwerp in 1576 – the so-called Spanish Fury. Silvius had to pay a large ransom to ensure the safety of his family and his business. This proved the straw that broke the camel's back. By the end of the 1570s he decided to move his publishing house to Leiden, where he was offered the job of academic printer of the newly founded university. Silvius died unexpected in 1580 and his son, Carel, took over the company. The expensive relocation to Leiden and Willem Silvius' sudden death meant the end of his printing shop. By 1582, Carel had to file for bankruptcy. Most of the stock of The Golden Angel was bought by Plantin, who had also moved to Leiden to open up the second printing office of the *Officina Plantiniana*.¹⁴

⁹ Valkema Blouw, op. cit. (n. 6), p. 428.

¹⁰ For more information on the Antwerp Landjuweel of 1561, see J.J.M. Vandommele, *Als in een spiegel. Vrede, kennis en gemeenschap op het Antwerpse Landjuweel van 1561* (Hilversum 2011) and R. Ryckaert, *De Antwerpse spelen van 1561, naar de editie Silvius (Antwerpen 1562)* (Gent 2011).

¹¹ Valkema Blouw, op. cit. (n. 6), p. 435.

¹² See A. Rouzet, *Dictionnaire des imprimeurs, librairies et éditeurs des XVe et XVIe siècles dans les limites géographiques de la Belgique actuelle* (Nieuwkoop 1975), pp. 201-202.

¹³ Rouzet, op. cit. (n. 12), pp. 201.

¹⁴ Rouzet, op. cit. (n. 12), pp. 201-202; P. Valkema Blouw, 'The Leiden « afdrucksel » : a type specimen of the press of Willem Silvius in its last days (1582), in: *Dutch Typography in the Sixteenth Century. The Collected Works of Paul Valkema Blouw*, ed. T. Croiset van Uchelen and Paul Dijstelberge (Leiden/Boston 2013), pp. 33-7.

Silvius' Interest in the Art of Writing

In the history of the sixteenth-century Antwerp printing press, Silvius' publications are well known for using different kinds of typography. For example, in his edition of the aforementioned *Spelen van sinne vol scoone moralisacien wtleggingen* (1562), the theatre plays are set in the commonly used *Textura*, while the title page and the prefaces use several *Roman* fonts, as well as *Schwabacher* and *Civilité*.¹⁵ In all probability, Silvius' experiments with typography are connected to his interest in promoting the art of writing. This interest developed early in his printing career. Together with Plantin and Tavenier, Silvius was one of the first printers in Antwerp who published typographical writing-books for the purpose of teaching handwriting in primary schools and private tuition.

Typographical writing-books were published in oblong format and set in *Civilité*, which resembled best the Gothic cursive hand. They contain 23 leaves (or more), with every page comprising of the alphabet set in lower (and sometimes upper) case *Civilité* and a short religious and moralising text, beginning with a large decorated initial.¹⁶ They derived from abecedaries or ABC-books, which were immensely popular in the booming city of Antwerp, that, during its heyday in the 1560s, had between 150 and 250 primary schools ('cleyne scholen').¹⁷ Ton Croiset van Uchelen, who researched Dutch typographical writing-books extensively, established that Silvius published four typographical writing-books in the 1560s (one in Dutch and three in French), all of which were based on texts by the famous Dutch writer Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert.¹⁸ He also found that from 1563 until 1570, Silvius inserted single-leaf writing exemplars into his other publications. These single-leaf pages are rather extraordinary: instead of typeset, they contain woodcuts that reproduce texts written by Willem Silvius himself in the Italian handwriting style, the so-called *cancellaresca* or chancery script. Clearly meant to be used as writing models to be copied, Croiset van Uchelen argued that Silvius should be viewed as a champion of the use of the Italian hand in writing.¹⁹

¹⁵ Valkema Blouw, op. cit. (n. 6), p. 439; Ryckaert, op. cit. (n. 10), p. 61.

¹⁶ De la Fontaine Verwey, op. cit. (n. 3), passim; Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 5: 1980), p. 110.

¹⁷ G. Vanpaemel, 'Science for sale: the metropolitan stimulus for scientific achievements in sixteenth century Antwerp', in: *Urban achievement in Early Modern Europe*, ed. P. O'Brien (Cambridge 2001), p. 295.

¹⁸ Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert, *Eenen nieuwen ABC of Materi-boeck, inhoudende diuersche schoone sententien ende leeringhen, soo wel tot verlichtinghe der schoolmeesters, als tot dienst, ende behulp der iongers ende maechdekens, die gheen bequaemheyt en hebben om te gheraken by meesters die fraeye handelinghe vande penne hebben* (Antwerp, Willem Silvius, 1564). Copies: University Library Amsterdam (OTM: KL 08-29); Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert, *Nouvel Exemple pour apprendre à écrire, contenant plusieurs belles sentences* (Antwerp, Willem Silvius, 1565). Copies: Newberry Library (Wing ZW 5465 .S587); Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert, *Nouvel Exemple pour apprendre à écrire, contenant plusieurs belles sentences* (Antwerp, Willem Silvius, 1567). Copies: British Library (C.119.c.14.); Dirck Volckertszoon Coornhert, *Nouvel Exemple pour apprendre à écrire, contenant plusieurs belles sentences* (Antwerp, Willem Silvius, 1568). Copies: Zentralbibliothek Zürich (KK 1045,4), British Library (C.119.c.13.). In 1980 Croiset van Uchelen misidentified the Newberry copy as an initial book, instead of the first French edition of the Coornhert's typographical writing-book. Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 5:1980), pp. 109-134. Silvius also published three ordinary ABC-poems set in *Civilité* during his Antwerp period.

¹⁹ Croiset van Uchelen found seven different single-leaf pages in nine Silvius editions from the period 1563-1570. T. Croiset van Uchelen, 'Willem Silvius as writing-master', in: *Theatrum orbis librorum. Liber amicorum*

After 1568, Silvius seemed to have left the publication of writing-books to other printers. Yet he continued to inform himself on new developments. On the 25th of October 1570 he wrote a certain Pieter vanden Kerckhoff in London to request being send an English writing-book by a 'zeker François' [a certain Frenchman].²⁰ This must have been *A Booke containing divers sortes of hands, as well the English as French secretarie with the Italian, Roman, chancelry & court hands* (Thomas Vautrollier, 1570), the first English exemplar book, which was written by the French writing master John De Beauguesne (1538? -after 1610). Similarly to Silvius, De Beauguesne was a great admirer of the Italian hand and his writing manual contains several examples of this style.

Silvius' interest in publishing educational books about handwriting can partially be explained by looking at his professional life before he became a printer. In one of his early publications, a Latin schoolbook by the Amsterdam teacher Johannes Sartorius (c. 1500-1557), titled *Selectissimarum orationum Germanice redditarum delectissimus*, published in 1563, Silvius writes that he used to have a career as a writing master and taught the art of writing at the university of Louvain to 'sons of princely houses' ('Cum superioribus annis in academia Lovaniensi principum aliquot filios instituendos accepissem'²¹), specifically instructing them to write and reproduce the Italian hand, which was - according to him - not only elegant ('adspectu elegans est') and easy to read ('ac lectu periuicunda'), but useful ('utilitates'), because it made taking dictations of university lectures so much simpler.²² We know for certain that Silvius did indeed live in Louvain. He registered his name in the matricula of the Louvain university on the third of February 1550 and graduated eight years later as a law student of the 'Collegium Porci'.²³ However, without any strong evidence to back up Silvius' claims, his years as a successful writing master in Louvain were mere conjecture. The discovery of his own writing-book gives us new insight into his writing ability and his professional connections.

Silvius' Writing-book

The writing-book of Willem Silvius has an oblong octavo format (155x220 mm). It counts 49 vellum leaves in a gold-tooled red morocco binding. The first folio serves as a title-page and reads: *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum a Gulielmo Sylvio Regio Typographo scripta sculpta & in lucem edita. Anno 1562* [=Examples of various scripts for the benefit of students of this art, written, cut and printed by Willem Silvius, royal printer in the year 1562] (fig. 1).²⁴ Even though this leaf is precisely dated, the second folio of the

presented to Nico Israel on the occasion of his seventieth birthday, ed. T. Croiset van Uchelen, K. Van der Horst & G. Schilder (Utrecht, 1989), p. 159.

²⁰ *Epistulae et Tractatus cum Reformationis tum Ecclesiae Londino-Batavae Historiam Illustrantes: Ecclesiae Londino-Batavae Archivum*, ed. J. H. Hessels, vol. 3, pt. 1 (Cambridge, 1897), pp. 123–4.

²¹ Johannes Sartorius, *Selectissimarum orationum Germanice redditarum delectissimus* (Antwerp, Willem Silvius, 1563), p. 83.

²² Sartorius, op. cit. (n. 21), p. 83; Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 19), p. 174.

²³ *Matricule de l'université de Louvain*, ed. A.H. Schillings, vol. 4 (Brussel 1961-1966), p. 402; *Analecta pour servir à l'histoire ecclésiastique*, 3 (1866), p. 467.

²⁴ *Kalligrafische bundel van Willem Silvius*. KB The Hague, MS KW 129 F 2.

manuscript suggests an earlier date of creation, as it carries the inscription ‘Guilielmus Sylvius Buscoducensis scribebat Lovanij Anno à Nativitate Domini 1550’ [=Willem Sylvius of Den Bosch wrote this in Louvain, in the year of the birth of our Lord 1550] (fig. 2). In all likelihood, Sylvius started making writing examples on sheets of vellum in 1550, when he began his life as a writing master in Louvain. Such sheets were common among the profession and were used to advertise the penmanship of the writing master to potential customers.²⁵ Some twelve years later, in 1561-1562, Sylvius must have decided to publish an exemplar book about his ‘art’, the first of its kind to be published in the Low Countries. To this end, he created the title-page on folio 1 and brought together a strong and diverse collection of his writing examples to use as a setting copy for the printed edition. Around this time he also requested the already mentioned privilege for a ‘certain book of diverse handwritings’ and started to publish single leaf exemplars in some of his books. Sylvius was clearly experimenting, reproducing his Italian writing models in woodcut to assess their quality while at the same time exploring the demand for such products. The woodcut exemplars must not have achieved the desired result, since he never published his writing book. Instead, from 1564 onwards, he started to produce typographical abecedaries.

The first folio of the writing-book further contains a clue concerning the provenance of the manuscript. In 1608, a previous owner wrote his name on the leaf: ‘Cornelius à Pelanen, Jacobi F., G. Sylvy Nepos 1608’. Cornelis van Polanen was the son of Willem Sylvius’ daughter, Sara, who had married Jacob van Polanen, a teacher of the French School in Leiden in 1585.²⁶ As Sylvius’ grandson, Cornelius must have inherited the writing-book through his mother and might even have used it for his own educational practices. Only in the late eighteenth century did the manuscript receive its current morocco binding and gilded edge, which were made in Leiden by the ‘Eerste dissertatie’ bookbindery.²⁷ In all likelihood, it was at that point already in possession of the Orange Stadtholders. It stayed in the Stadtholder’s library in The Hague until 1816, when king Willem I of the Netherlands bestowed it to the Dutch National Library.²⁸

Apart from the two folia that serve as title-pages, the manuscript contains 44 leaves with writing examples (also called ‘models’) by Sylvius, all of which are written on the recto side of the page. The exemplars are in several types of script and in no less than eight different languages. Fourteen folia have a colored background (brick-red, blue, yellow or black) on which the letters are written in colored ink. The book also contains three full page gouaches. On folio 3 for example, a beautiful colored cartouche contains the German inscription: ‘Die

²⁵ S.H. Steinberg, ‘Medieval writing-masters’, in: *The Library* 22 (1941), pp. 2-3; R.J. Resoort, ‘Een proper profitelijc boek’. Eind vijftiende en zestiende eeuw’, in: *De hele Bibelebontse berg*, ed. N. Heimeriks (e.a.) (Amsterdam, 1989), pp. 75-6; Fr. Van der Heyden, ‘A writing master’s Sheet from the Low Countries. An investigation of the writing Master’s Sheet (Harderwijk, Streekarchivariaat Noordwest-Veluwe, MS OAH 2002)’, in: *Quaerendo*, 46 (2016), p. 301.

²⁶ Erfgoed en Omstreken Leiden (ELO), Oud Notarieel archief (ONA) inv. 50, f.54; Idem, NH Ondertrouw A. 1575 - maart 1586, archiefnummer 1004, Nederlands Hervormd Ondertrouw (1575-1795), inventarisnummer 1, blad A - 180v.

²⁷ J. Storm van Leeuwen, *Dutch decorated bookbinding in the eighteenth century*. Vol. 3 (‘t Goy-Houten 2006), p. 259.

²⁸ Th. Lunsingh Scheurleer, *150 jaar Koninklijke Kabinet van Schilderijen. Koninklijke Bibliotheek. Koninklijk Penningkabinet* (Den Haag 1967), p. 96.

welt vergeht mit irer lust / wer aber den willn gottes thut / der bleibt in ewigkeit', taken from the Gospel of John (John 1, 2:17) (fig. 3). Another gouache, on folio 4, depicts the alliance coat of arms of the Egmond-Van Bergen-Glymes family (more about this coat of arms later) (fig. 4). The book concludes with the triumphal Christ standing in an archway.

Silvius' writing-book starts off with some high quality calligraphy. On folio 5, an impressive rendition of the Latin epigram by the Italian humanist Giovanni Pontano (1426-1503) is created in the Italian hand: 'Integritate fides alitur, & fide vero amicitia' [=Integrity supports loyalty and loyalty improves true friendship] (fig. 5). Though remarkable, this kind of lavish calligraphy is not the focus of the manuscript. Most writing examples are functional in scope and are oriented towards the practice of writing and using different styles of script for different occasions. This educational emphasis is confirmed at the beginning of the book, which reproduces four distinctive alphabets, with one or two leaves for each different style of alphabet: starting with a *Textur*-style capital and minuscule (ff. 7-8), a *Roman*-style capital (f. 9), a *Fraktur*-versal letter (f. 10) and an ornamental capital with extensive plaiting (ff. 11-12). After this introduction, Silvius arranged his writing-book per language. First, various German language scripts (9 folia) are presented. They are followed by Dutch (2 folia), French (3 folia), Spanish (2 folia), Italian (1 folio) and Latin (16 folia) scripts. The last two languages are Greek (2 folia) and Hebrew (1 folio). The writing examples depict different legal, mercantile and secretary hands, most of which are derived from the gothic script, although the Italian hand, or *cancellaresca corsiva* is also accounted for in case of the Latin writing models.

Almost every sheet contains an alphabet in small letters and sometimes in capitals as well. Text fragments on the same folio are always written in the specific hand of the presented alphabet. They function as demonstrations of how the alphabet could be utilized within a certain context. Because the great variety of, and nuance in scripts displayed, classification of all the specific hands should best be left to a calligraphy expert. It goes without saying that writing-masters were expected to have mastered a great variety of hands. In their writing-books, they preferred to vary in these handwritings to show off their skill and ingenuity.²⁹ Silvius' manuscript is no different.

Similarly, the content of the text fragments is very diverse. Sheets often contain models to be used for starting a letter, offering standard salutations to be used in diplomatic correspondence, for instance the decorum when writing to highborn princes, such as 'Dem Durchleuchtigen Hochgebornen Fursten und hern, Hern N. Marggraven zu Branndenburg' or 'Dem Durchleuchtigen Hochgebornnen Fursten und Hern, Hern Wilhelm von Gottes genaden Printzen zu Oranien'. Other pages show examples of business correspondence, for instance folio 14, which consists of a notary contract which describes a bond of five guilders, owed by three German students to a certain 'Lamprechten Selltenreich' [=Lambrecht Seldom Rich]. Most fragments contain similar fictions. By alternating in style and genre, Silvius intended to show the wide range of possibilities within a certain style of handwriting. Not only letters and contracts are simulated, he also writes down examples that contain Biblical quotations,

²⁹ Steinberg, op. cit. (n. 25), p. 2; A.R.A. Croiset van Uchelen, 'Abraham van Overbeke, an early seventeenth century writing master from Zeeland', in: *Quaerendo* 2 (1972), p. 283.

religious prayers and passages from the writings of classical authors such as Cicero, Cato, Seneca and Marcus Aurelius. As such, his writing-book would have been able to cater to the interests of a broad variety of clients, whether those interest would be educational, professional, religious or intellectual.³⁰

Silvius' sources

Croiset van Uchelen saw Silvius as the direct heir to Gerard Mercator (1512-1594), who was the first in the Low Countries to publish guidelines about how to master the art of writing in the Italian hand.³¹ In his *Literarum latinarum, quas italicas, cursoriasque vocant, scribendarum ratio*, first published in 1540, Mercator went into great detail explaining the use of the Italian hand or *cancellaresca* script. He describes how the quill should be used, what the right proportions were of the Italian letter, how to create the perfect angle for the letters and how and when to use decorative flourish. He cut the woodblocks for the script himself, so he was sure of the quality of the reproduction.³² Mercator considered the Italian hand or *cancellaresca* script to be superior to most other scripts, specifically because of its elegance and readability.³³ As already mentioned, Silvius sometimes inserted woodcut single-leaf pages with this Italian script into his pedagogical publications, which shows he was indeed an adherent of the Italian hand. The The Hague manuscript confirms this. It contains many examples of *cancellaresca* script, some of which are very similar to the single-leaf pages that Silvius published after 1563, even using the same text. The Italian and most of the Latin text fragments (folia 29-35) are all written in variants of the Italic *cancellaresca* script.

Silvius seemed to have wanted to stress this connection to Mercator in the writing-book. In a curious writing example on folio 35, Mercator's name is mentioned (Fig.6). The fragment reads as follows: 'IN Christi nomine Amen. Anno a Nativitate eiusdem Millesimo quingentesimo quinquagesimo die vero sabbati quinta Julij Lovanij in domo habitationis honesti iuxta ac probi viri Mⁱ. Adriani Hollar. Acta fuerunt hec Lovanij presentibus honorabilibus viris M^s Arnoldo Merbecio. Illustrissumi Principis Auraici pędagogo. Gerardo Mercatore Rupelmondano & Laurentio Voglio testibus ad etcx' [=In the name of Christ, Amen. Anno 1550 after the birth of Christ, Louvain, on Sunday the 5th day of July, invited to the house of the honest and trustworthy man, master Adrianus of Hollar. These things were done in Louvain, in the presence of the honourable master Arnoldus van Merbec. The teacher of the illustrious prince of Orange. Witnessed by Gerard Mercator of Rupelmonde and Laurentius Voglius]. Laurentius Voglius and Arnoldus van Merbec both appear in the matricula of the

³⁰ M. van der Wal and G. Rutten, 'The practice of letter writing. Skills, models and early modern Dutch manuals', in: *Language and history* 56 (2013), pp. 27-8.

³¹ Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 5:1980), p. 159.

³² A.S. Osley, *Mercator. A monograph on the lettering of maps* (London 1969), pp. 20-21; Nicolas Crane, *Mercator: the man who mapped the planet* (London 2010), pp. 113-114.

³³ Gerardus Mercator, *Literarum latinarum, quas italicas, cursoriasque vocant, scribendarum ratio* (1540, Louvain, Rutger Rescius), f. A2r. Digital Copy of Regensburg, Staatliche Bibliothek -- 999/4Hist.lit .127.

Louvain university (respectively in 1543 and in 1551).³⁴ They must have been fellow students of Silvius. Gerard Mercator was also living in Louvain around that time, teaching students while developing handwriting that could be used for his cartographic work.³⁵ Was Silvius one of those student under his charge? It would explain how Silvius got to know the *cancellaresca* script. The fragment in the writing-book suggests that Silvius might have had a closer connection to Mercator than research has previously supposed. Moreover, at that time Mercator was already in close contact with John Dee, the scholar who was to become Queen Elizabeth I her royal astrologer. Dee published his *Monas hieroglyphica* with the Silvius press in 1564 and stayed at Silvius' house in Antwerp while writing the manuscript.³⁶ Mercator could have easily introduced Silvius to Dee as early as 1550.

Apart from this reference, it is also worth mentioning that Silvius' style of writing is very reminiscent of the Italian writing masters Giovanni Antonio Tagliente (c. 1460s – c. 1528), Ludovico degli Arrighi (1475-1527) and Giovanni Battista Palatino (1515-1575), all of whom published their writing-books on *cancellaresca* script in Italy during the early sixteenth century (Tagliente's *Lo presente libro insegna la vera arte delo excellēte scriuere de diuerse varie sorti de litere* in 1524, Arrighi's *La operina di Ludovico Vicentino, da imparare di scrivere littera Cancellarescha* in 1527 and Palatino's *Libro Nuovo D'Imparare A Scrivere Tutte Sorte Lettere Antiche Et Moderne Di Tutte Nationi* in 1540), which were reprinted in Antwerp in the 1540s and 1550s.³⁷ Comparing woodcuts of the books of the last two calligraphers with the Silvius manuscript, one can see clearly how Silvius had the intention to replicate their style. With Arrighi, it is especially apparent if one compares the plaited ornamental capitals (fig. 7-8). Palatino's book seems to have functioned as a direct example, as the folio's of the French hand and the Cancellaresca script show (fig. 9-12). The leaf with the Latin abbreviations was also clearly inspired by the Italian calligraphers (fig. 13-14).

Silvius' writing-book even concludes by copying a calligraphic highpoint he must have learned while studying Palatino's handbook. On one of the last pages of the book, four different biblical citations about brotherly love are recorded in five different languages (Dutch, French, German, Latin and Greek) in mirror writing (fig. 15-16). All start with an ornamental capital and are written in gold ink. A text in *cancellaresca* script is in cartouche above the mirror writing. The text reads: 'Non bisogno sospender piu la mente, Ch'allo speichio si legge la presente' [=One does not have to break one's head thinking about this, what you see here is all written in mirror writing.]. This is a direct quote taken from Palatino's writing-book, in which the Italian writing master demonstrated his skill in *Lettera Macina* (mirror writing) (Fig. 15-16). As this is one of the last pages of the manuscript, Silvius clearly must have meant to

³⁴ *Matricule de l'université de Louvain*, op. cit. (n. 23), pp. 268, 444.

³⁵ Osley, op. cit. (n. 32), pp. 51-4; T. Croiset van Uchelen, 'Het schrift en de kalligrafie', in: M. Watelet (ed.), *Gerardus Mercator Rupelmundanus* (Antwerpen 1994), pp. 157-59.

³⁶ S. Clucas, 'The Royal Typographer and the Alchemist: John Dee, Willem Silvius, and the Diagrammatic Alchemy of the Monas Hieroglyphica', in: *Ambix*, 64 (2017), pp. 141-44.

³⁷ These Italian writing books were very popular in Antwerp and Joannes van der Loe (1506-1563) reprinted these books a number of times: Tagliente in 1545 en 1550 and Arrighi in 1543, 1545 and 1546.

emulate Palatino's aptitude. As a final demonstration of his own artifice, he showed that his own remarkable skill as writing master was comparable to that of the Italian masters.

Had Silvius published his writing book, it would have been the first Dutch exemplar book that showed a variety of styles of handwriting in a multitude of language – Mercator's *Literarum latinarum* had only produced woodcuts of the Italian hand. It would also have been one of the first exemplar books in Europe published in the oblong format, a practice that just started to become popular in the 1550s to cater better to the needs of clerks and business correspondents. However, both in style of handwriting and selection of texts, Silvius his writing book has more in common with older exemplar books. As already mentioned, his handwriting scripts often feel restrained, more focused on being functional than aesthetically pleasing. Similarly, his selection of texts are directly related to the practice of writing professionally, whether that was in a scholarly context or for business or diplomatic correspondence. This is in stark contrast to later Dutch exemplar books, which frequently include embellished scripts to be more visually pleasing to the customer.³⁸

The Orange connection

The writing-book does not only contain clues concerning the calligraphers that might have influenced Willem Silvius in the 1550s. It also confirms certain speculations about Silvius' connection to the house of Orange-Nassau.³⁹ This connection was obvious in his later life, as by 1575, Silvius used his printing press to publicly support the Dutch Revolt and its leader William of Orange (1533-1584).⁴⁰ Croiset van Uchelen noted that Marcus van Vaernewijck described Willem Silvius in his *Van die beroerlicke tijden in die Nederlanden en voornamelick in Ghendt* (1566-1568) as the printer who 'formerly taught the children of the Prince of Orange, as a schoolmaster, and thus became an acquaintance of the aforementioned prince' ['die wijlen die kinderen vanden prince van Oraingien, als schoolmeester, gheleert hadde, ende was bij dien in de kenneſſe vanden voornoemden prince ghecommen'].⁴¹ A similar description can be found in a letter from an Italian diplomat in Brussels, Niccolò Carezone, to Francis Walsingham in 1578, in which the Italian commends Silvius as the 'governor of the sons [sic] of the Prince of Orange at the University of Louvain'.⁴² Connecting these remarks to the testimony of Silvius himself that he had taught the art of writing at the university of Louvain to 'sons of princely houses', Croiset van Uchelen concluded that Silvius must have

³⁸ Dutch writing masters from the late sixteenth and early seventeenth century seemed to have used the exemplar books of Clemens Perret (c. 1551—1591) as a model for their own publications, with more imaginative and artistic calligraphy within richly decorated borders. See T. Croiset van Uchelen, 'The mysterious writing-master Clemens Perret', in: *Quaerendo*, 17 (1987), pp. 14, 27-28.

³⁹ Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 5:1980), pp. 175-76.

⁴⁰ P. Valkema Blouw, 'Willem Silvius, Christiaan Houweel and anti-Spanish propaganda, 1577 to 1579', in: *Quaerendo*, 24 (1994), pp. 20-29.

⁴¹ Marcus van Vaernewijck, *Van die beroerlicke tijden in die Nederlanden en voornamelick in Ghendt, 1566-1568*, ed. F. Vanderhaeghen, vol. 3 (Gent 1872-1881), p. 134.

⁴² *Calendar of State Papers, Foreign Series, of the Reign of Elizabeth: Preserved in the State Paper Department of Her Majesty's Public Record Office, 1577-1578*, ed. A.J. Crosby & J. Stevenson, vol. 12 (London 1966), p. 251.

instructed the siblings of William of Orange who were living in Breda from the early 1550s onwards, specifically his sisters Juliana, Maria and Magdalena van Nassau.⁴³

The writing-book makes a strong case for connecting Silvius to William of Orange. The prince is mentioned twice in the manuscript: once in an example of a diplomatic letter in German and once in the text sample that also mentioned Arnoldus van Merbec as instructor to the prince (see above). Originally from Eigenbrakel, van Merbec also called himself Nyvella (of Nivelles). He became a priest (rector magister) in Breda in 1550.⁴⁴ Furthermore, the alliance coat of arms of the Egmond-Van Bergen-Glymes on the third page of the manuscript, was created for Margareta of Glymes (1486-1551) when she married Floris of Egmond (1469-1539). Both were the paternal grandparents of Anna van Buren, the first wife of William of Orange. The presence of the coat of arms in the beginning of writing-book suggests that Silvius either was close to the family of Anna van Buren, or that he intended to dedicate the book to the family, hoping to receive its patronship.

In her study on the court of William of Orange, Marie-Ange Delen mentions that the inventory of the Breda castle reveals that two writing tables were bought by Anna van Buren in 1553, presumably to be used for writing classes. At that moment, the court of Breda already contained several boys from noble families that had been send to William of Orange to serve as pages. The brothers and sisters of the prince were also present around that time.⁴⁵ It is certainly feasible that Willem Silvius served as a part time writing master at the court during his studies in Louvain, assisting Arnoldus van Merbec. After the death of Anna van Buren in 1558, Silvius must have left this position in Breda to set up his printing shop in Antwerp. Orange might even have helped getting him his first printing assignment. The prince was certainly in a good position to recommend him for the publication of the Latin and French edition of the statutes of the Order of the Golden Fleece in 1558-1559.

Conclusion

From 1550 until 1558, Willem Silvius was a writing master at the University of Louvain. During this time, he produced a writing-book which contained several writing styles in a number of languages: German, Dutch, French, Spanish, Italian, Latin, Greek and Hebrew. In 1561, Silvius – now a printer in Antwerp – requested a privilege for the publication of this writing-book, which he gave the title *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*. It would have been the first printed writing-book of a Dutch writing master that contained models for different languages and circumstances. Although the privilege was granted on the 5th of January 1562, the publication never materialised. For some reason, Silvius decided

⁴³ The children of William of Orange and his first wife, Anna van Buren, were only born in 1553 (Mary), 1554 (Filip William) and 1556 (Mary). They were too young to have benefited from a skilled writing master. Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 19), pp. 175-176.

⁴⁴ G.C.A. Juten, 'Consilium de Beke', in: *Taxandria, Tijdschrift voor Noordbrabantsche geschiedenis en volkskunde* 26 (1919), p. 208.

⁴⁵ M. Delen, *Het hof van Willem van Oranje* (Amsterdam 2002), p. 147; Croiset van Uchelen, op. cit. (n. 19), p. 176.

against the printing of the manuscript. The following years, Silvius did publish writing manuals, but now only abecedaries, typographical writing-books and single-leaf exemplars. The single-leaf exemplars, cut out of woodblocks, show examples of the Italian hand and are no doubt inspired by the writing examples of the manuscript. But why did Silvius not publish his whole writing-book?

In all likelihood, Silvius could not find any artisan with the required skill to cut the writing models in relief. Even if possible, such a publication would have been very expensive.⁴⁶ Silvius might also have doubted the quality of woodcut reproductions for imitating his exceptional hand. Exemplar books in woodcut had difficulty with mimicking finer details. Only in 1569 were Dutch printers able to produce qualitative reproductions by using copperplate engravings, first of which was the writing book of Brussels writing master Clemens Perret (c. 1551—1591). By that time Silvius was financially in bad weather and he never risked such an investment. Moreover, Perret started a new style of writing-book, which focussed more on lavish calligraphy. Silvius' manuscript, which used the old Italian writing-books as a template, might have looked old-fashioned by comparison. His writing-book therefore remained unpublished and even disappeared from view after his death. Only in the 18th century did the manuscript reappear, now in the collection of the Orange-Nassau family. How it came to be in that collection is unknown, but the strong bond between Willem Silvius and William of Orange must have played a part in its procurement. When the writing-book was acquired by the KB, it remained unidentified until recently. It now has reclaimed its important place in the history of handwriting in the Early Modern Low Countries.

⁴⁶ T. Croiset van Uchelen, 'Jodocus Hondius's *Theatrum artis scribendi* examined anew', in: *Quaerendo*, 34 (2004), pp. 60.

Images

Fig. 1: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 1r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 2: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 2r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 3: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 3r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 4: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 4r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 7: Ludovico degli Arrighi, *La operina di Ludovico Vincentino, da imparare di scrivere lettera cancellares cha* (Antwerpen, Johannes Loe 1543), KB KW 1702 C 27, fol. F3v-4r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 8: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 11r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 9: Giovanni Battista Palatino, *Libro Nuovo D'Imparare A Scrivere Tutte Sorte Lettere Antiche Et Moderne Di Tutte Nationi* (Rome 1540), Wing ZW 535.P173, fol. G3r (The Newberry Library, Chicago).

Fig.10: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 10r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 11: Giovanni Battista Palatino, *Libro Nuovo D'Imparare A Scrivere Tutte Sorte Lettere Antiche Et Moderne Di Tutte Nationi* (Rome 1540), Wing ZW 535.P173, fol. D4r (The Newberry Library, Chicago).

Fig. 12: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 31r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).

Fig. 15: Giovanni Battista Palatino, *Libro Nuovo D'Imparare A Scrivere Tutte Sorte Lettere Antiche Et Moderne Di Tutte Nationi* (Rome 1540), Wing ZW 535.P173, fol. G3v (The Newberry Library, Chicago).

Fig. 16: Willem Silvius, *Variarum scripturarum exempla in gratiam huius artis studiosorum*, 1550-1562, KB KW 129 F 2, fol. 47r (Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Den Haag).